

Active role of lagging chromosomes in spindle collapse as revealed by live phase contrast and tubulin immunostaining in grasshopperspermatocytes.

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Abstract

Univalents, that is, chromosomes lacking an attached partner at the first meiotic division, show extremely faulty transmission. Most segregational errors stem from amphitelic (mitotic-like) orientation at metaphase I followed by anaphase I lagging. Our studies in living grasshopper spermatocytes show that amphitelic orientation may provoke spindle collapse: spindle elongation and cytokinesis are impaired and an unreduced restitution nucleus is formed. This does not prevent meiotic progression and eventually leads to the production of diploid gametes. The morphology and characteristics of spindle collapse in our material, as revealed by *in vivo* observation and tubulin immunostaining, indicate an active role of the chromosomes in the whole process.

Key words: Cell division, Mitotic spindle apparatus, Centrosome, Microtubules, Tubulin.

Introduction

Univalents are chromosomes lacking an attached counterpart at the first meiotic division. In accordance with the rule in this division, the two sister kinetochores of univalents tend to behave as a unit in their interactions with the spindle (syntely). As a consequence, as long as syntely is maintained, univalents have no possibility of bipolar stabilisation so they behave like mono-oriented chromosomes, undergoing successive interpolar movements with frequent changes in direction – reorientations – throughout prometaphase I. As prometaphase proceeds, the two sister kinetochores progressively become more distinct structures (Goldstein 1981; Janicke and LaFountain 1989; Rufas et al. 1989, 1994) and there is an increasing chance that, after a late reorientation, each will attach to a different pole and a persistent mitotic-like orientation (amphitelic) be achieved, stabilised by opposing tension forces (Wagenaar and Bray 1973; Rebollo and Arana 1995, 1998).

Univalents with a syntelic orientation at onset of anaphase I flawlessly divide reductionally and migrate to the poles simultaneously with the separating half-bivalents. By contrast, univalents that have acquired amphi-orientation at metaphase I are always delayed at anaphase I, remaining at the equator as lagging chromosomes well after the normally dividing chromosomes have finished their migration to the poles. Lagging is a consequence of persistent sister chromatid cohesion at the centromeric regions, which in meiosis is retained until anaphase II (Suja et al. 1992; Miyazaki and Orr-Weaver 1994; Bickel and Orr-Weaver 1996).

Anaphase I laggards may segregate in a variety of fashions including reductional and equational segregation, migration failure, and spindle collapse (see Rebollo and Arana 1997, 1998). If a pair of homologous univalents is considered, only the reductional segregation of each to a different pole would yield a normal genetic constitution in the resulting gametes. The remaining possibilities or any combination of them imply a great risk of producing gametes with abnormal numbers of chromosomes. This is the reason why univalency has long been recognised as the most frequent cause of aneuploidy. Syntelic univalents cannot congregate at the equator; hence they may be detected by the checkpoint mechanism that prevents anaphase onset in response to spindle defects or to faulty chromosome attachment and/or alignment (see Skibbens and Hieter 1998 for review).

The relationship between univalency and aneuploidy stands because this checkpoint is not very strict in certain systems, for instance, in mammalian female meiosis (LeMaire-Adkins et al. 1997). When univalents achieve amphitelic (mitotic-like) orientation, the consequences are potentially more harmful because these are chromosomes perfectly attached to the spindle and aligned at the metaphase plate, and so not candidates to be detected by the spindle checkpoint mechanism. Laggards may nevertheless produce aneuploidy since all kinds of segregation, including reductional segregation, are possible after anaphase I lagging (see Rebollo and Arana 1998). Moreover, as will be shown later in further detail, not only aneuploidy but also polyploidy is associated with univalency. Polyploidy occurs by nuclear restitution, which is the restoration of the diploid number of chromosomes by means other than normal fertilisation. In nature, meiotic restitution is associated with two different phenomena: parthenogenesis (apomixis in plants) and hybridisation. Although the mechanisms of restitution are very variable and not always associated with the presence of univalents (for review see Harlan and de Wet 1975; D'Amato 1977; Cuéllar 1987), a causal relationship between univalency and restitution in the first division of meiosis has been repeatedly reported from the earliest observations of this phenomenon. In plants, the *Taraxacum* type of diploid (unreduced) parthenogenesis is characterised by almost complete asynapsis followed by restitution at anaphase I and a normal second division (D'Amato 1977). In animals the process of meiotic restitution is not so well studied (Moritz 1984; see also White 1973; D'Amato 1977; Cuéllar 1987 for review) but it has also been related to the presence of univalents in interspecific hybrids and meiotic mutants of grasshoppers (John and Weissman 1977; Giménez-Abián et al. 1997). When it is not a characteristic of particular life cycles, polyploidy represents an important factor of reproductive impairment: in humans, polyploidy is the second most frequent cause of chromosomal abnormality and reproductive wastage (Carr and Gedeon 1977; Hook 1985; Hassold 1986; Jacobs and Hassold 1995).

The present study of the behaviour of univalents in cultured grasshopper meiocytes, combined with tubulin immunostaining of cells previously tracked *in vivo*, demonstrates a **causal relationship between chromosome lagging at anaphase and polyploidy**. In these cells, restitution occurs mainly at the first anaphase and is compatible with meiotic progression, at least until the spermatid stage, potentially rendering highly unsuitable gametes and/or embryos if fertilisation occurs. The mechanism causing restitution is what we called “**spindle collapse**” (Rebollo and Arana 1997): after anaphase onset, spindle poles, instead of separating, approach each other until the two chromosomal masses associated with them fuse, cleavage does not take place at the equator and the nuclear envelope reassembles around a single unreduced nucleus. Lagging chromosomes play an active role in the process of spindle collapse, which appears to be a direct consequence of normal anaphase activity in cells with chromosomes abnormally positioned in the spindle. Noticeably enough, very few laggards are capable of producing this phenomenon.

Materials and methods

Cultures were made following the technique of Nicklas et al. (1982) from testicular follicles obtained by biopsy from young adult males of the grasshopper species *Eyprepocnemis plorans* and *Locusta migratoria*. Meiotic progression of the cells was monitored by phase contrast in a Nikon Labophot-2 microscope. This permitted a direct comparison of the sequence of meiotic events in collapsing and non-collapsing cells. Phase contrast analysis also

allowed the recognition and selection of the distinct cellular landmarks used in the elaboration of the meiotic timetable and the precise identification of the cellular stage at the moment of fixation for immunostaining. In *E. plorans*, two types of natural univalents appear in male meiosis: the X chromosome, present in all cells, and different accessory chromosomes, appearing in low numbers in some individuals. Natural univalents are not involved in spindle collapse events (only two exceptional cases were scored for one accessory chromosome). In these experiments, the chromosomes involved in spindle collapses were autosomal univalents. Autosomal univalents sometimes appear spontaneously in normal individuals as a result of crossover failure. Usually only one pair of homologues is affected. Besides these rare cells, in structural heterozygotes of a grasshopper line carrying an A-B chromosome, resulting from a centric fusion between one B chromosome and the small-sized autosome S10, we found that the rearranged A-B chromosome, its normal S10 homologue, and, sometimes, one additional pair of autosomes appeared more often than usual as univalents. A total of 46 spontaneous univalents was analysed (see Table 1). In all these cultures, the majority of cells showed one single laggard at anaphase I.

Representative samples of cells with higher numbers of univalents and/or higher numbers of laggards could only be obtained by heat treatment. For the induction of autosomal univalents, young adult males were maintained at 44°C for 4 days and then allowed to recover under normal laboratory conditions (see Rebollo and Arana 1995). The presence of autosomal univalents was the only meiotic error found in these cells; no chromatin bridges or chromosome fragments were produced. The frequency of autosomal univalents per cell at prometaphase I varies depending on the time of recovery, yielding a characteristic response curve (Fig. 1). At first, cultures show a majority of cells devoid of univalents, the remaining cells possessing two to four autosomal univalents; we called these “early” univalents. Then, there is a sharp rise in the frequency of univalents and in the variance of the distribution: univalents appear in almost all cells, ranging from 2 to 22 in number; these univalents were called “intermediate”. After this maximum has been reached, the frequency of univalents abruptly decreases, most cells having no univalents or, occasionally, two to four; these were called “late” univalents. In order to classify univalents unequivocally within these three groups, only cultures showing a mean frequency of univalents of less than 1.5 per cell at prometaphase I were used as samples of early and late univalents. In the cultures included in the sample of intermediate univalents, the mean frequency of univalents per cell at prometaphase I ranges from 3.3 to 7.04. Owing to the variation between individuals found in this species in temporal response to heat, an additional estimation of the mean number of univalents per cell was performed for each individual the day after the *in vivo* analysis in order to confirm their placement either in the ascending or descending part of the response curve (see Fig. 1).

The segregation study carried out in *L. migratoria* is part of a more extensive experiment reported elsewhere (del Cerro et al., in preparation). We will deal here only with those aspects specific to spindle collapse. Heat treatment was similar to that of *E. plorans* except that the duration was 3 days and temperature 40°C. The cellular response was also comparable to that of *E. plorans*, with an abrupt peak of univalence on the 7th day and much lower inter-individual heterogeneity. Autosomal univalents were classified as early or late according to the same criteria used for *E. plorans* (Table 1). Neither intermediate nor spontaneous univalents were analysed in this species.

For the elaboration of the meiotic timetable of *E. plorans*, cultures comprised three control males and ten heat-treated males; two cultures per individual were analysed. Ten to 50 cells belonging to the same cyst were selected and tracked in each culture. Several milestones were chosen according to the ease of identification in the cultures under phase contrast; these are described in Fig. 2 and its legend.

Immunostaining techniques

Tubulin immunostaining was carried out on cultured spermatocytes previously tracked *in vivo*. When meiosis had progressed to the desired stage, cells were fixed and immunolabelled following the technique of Nicklas et al. (1995) for kinetochore staining with 3F3/2 antibody (Gorbsky and Ricketts 1993), but omitting microcystin LR in the lysis/fixative buffer. The labelled cells were examined with an epifluorescence Olympus BX 60 microscope with a 60×/1.25 oil immersion objective.

Results

The morphology of spindle collapse: live phase contrast imaging of collapsing cells

Spindle collapse markedly alters the morphology of dividing cells (see Fig. 3 for a comparison of collapsing and non-collapsing cells and diagrams in Fig. 2). In normal anaphase and telophase I, there is a marked spindle elongation while the mitochondrial mantle covering the spindle forms two dark lateral bands parallel to the spindle axis (Fig. 3B). As furrowing proceeds, these bands become progressively squeezed at the equator (Fig. 3C). In collapsing cells (Figs. 3A–D and 4A, B), laggards stay at the equator during anaphase I, while the reductionally separating chromosomes move to the poles; spindle elongation and normal cytokinesis are inhibited and the poles approach each other until the two telophase chromosomal masses associated with them are fused. A single nuclear envelope forms around the diploid restitution nucleus. During this process, cellular morphology changes dramatically: instead of the normal elongation followed by the formation of the cleavage furrow, the cells flatten, and the mitochondrial mantle covering the spindle can be seen as two extended lateral projections on the equatorial plane (see Figs. 3B, C, Fig. 4 A, 12 and 33 min prints, and Fig. 4B, 8 and 20 min prints). At late stages, unequivocal figures of spurious furrowing can be seen trapping the lateral projections (Fig. 4G). This is what is known as **complete spindle collapse**. However, less frequently, a variety of **incomplete forms of collapse** can be seen. The initial stages of collapse are the same but the two approaching chromosomal masses associated with the poles do not fuse and each reassembles its own nuclear envelope, producing two independent, but very close nuclei (Fig. 4C). Occasionally, when laggards are placed on one side of the spindle, this side shows the typical folding on the equatorial plane whereas the side free of univalents shows a pronounced curve devoid of lateral projections (Fig. 4D). Collapses may also occur in the second division when single chromatids originating from equational segregation of chromosomes at anaphase I attach to both poles and lag at the second anaphase (Fig. 4E, F). The process is very similar to that described before.

Tubulin immunofluorescence

Selected cysts containing cells with numerous univalents were tracked under phase contrast. Anaphase I and spindle collapse occurred in these cysts with a certain asynchrony. When individually tracked cells had progressed to different stages of collapse, the preparations were fixed and immunostained so that the fluorescent images could be unequivocally matched to the sequence obtained by phase contrast observation of live cells. Tubulin immunolabelling reveals a morphology fully concordant with that observed in phase contrast images. Figure 5A–I illustrates the successive stages of spindle collapse in *E. plorans* (Fig. 5E–I) compared with a normal first division (Fig. 5A–D). The morphology of second division collapses (Fig. 5J) also corresponds with the phase contrast images (see Fig. 5 legend for a detailed description).

Spindle collapse occurs only in cells with laggards

Except in those cultures where the number of univalents per cell is very high, cells with and without univalents co-exist within the same cyst. In cells with univalents, these orient syntelically or amphitelically independently from one another (Rebollo and Arana, unpublished). Univalents that oriented syntelically at anaphase I onset, segregate undivided to one of the poles, simultaneously with the normal bivalent-forming chromosomes. Amphitelic univalents lag at anaphase I. Only in those cells possessing amphioriented laggards is collapse a possible outcome; collapse was never seen in cells without laggards in the same cultures, even in those adjacent to collapsing cells. This implies that the presence of lagging chromosomes is necessary for the occurrence of spindle collapse. The possibility that spindle collapse is restricted to those cells that have suffered heat treatment during early prophase I can be ruled out since spontaneous univalents, appearing in animals not exposed to heat, can also be involved in collapse events (see Table 1, spontaneous univalents, and Fig. 3).

The probability of collapse depends on the number and the “quality” of laggards

Spindle collapse may occur in cells with one single lagging chromosome, but its probability increases with the number of laggards. A simple correlation between the number of laggards and the frequency of collapse could not be immediately established in our material, since we detected an additional influence of the cellular origin of the univalents, that is, there were differences between early and late induced univalents. Thus, it is not only the number, but also the quality of laggards that is important for the occurrence of spindle collapse.

As shown in Table 1, while the frequency of amphiorientation is the same for all the different categories of univalents within a species (early, intermediate, late, and spontaneous univalents in *E. plorans* and early and late in *L. migratoria*), the probability of equational segregation of laggards is much lower in early than in late univalents. As equational division is the only segregational outcome that implies a complete loss of sister chromatid cohesion at anaphase I, this indicates that late univalents have a weaker cohesion, probably due to a differential effect of heat treatment (Rebollo and Arana 1998; del Cerro et al., in preparation). In *E. plorans*, spontaneous univalents behave like the early-induced univalents, with 10% equational segregation. Differences between the groups of univalents also appear in the frequency of other segregational modes, for instance, spontaneous univalents of *E. plorans* show the highest frequency of reductional segregation after lagging (see Table 1).

An additional complication stems from the fact that, as those chromosomes lagging at anaphase I may still segregate reductionally or equationally, classification by number of laggards can be made on the basis of two different hypotheses:

1. From anaphase I onset, all the laggards present in one cell can contribute to an eventual spindle collapse, regardless of the particular segregation fate of each chromosome (provided that at least one persists until telophase). So, the laggards are to be counted at anaphase I.
2. Only those chromosomes persisting as laggards at telophase I contribute to spindle collapse. In this case, the laggards are to be counted at telophase I. Obviously, sample sizes are smaller than in the former case since some laggards end up segregating during the lapse between anaphase and telophase I.

Summing up, in order to test the influence of the number and the quality of laggards on the occurrence of spindle collapse, in *E. plorans*, cells within each of the four univalent origin groups, early, intermediate, late and spontaneous, were further classified by the number of laggards, and these were scored at two different stages, anaphase I and telophase I. In *L. migratoria*, the same procedure was applied to early and late univalents. Figure 6A, B shows the results obtained after classification in this way. The existence of a **positive correlation between the number of laggards and the frequency of collapse** is evident in all the categories of univalents. This correlation is best estimated for the intermediate univalents of *E. plorans*, where cells with three, four or more laggards are more frequent. G-tests for one to four laggards in intermediate univalents yield significant differences in both anaphase I laggards ($G=12.51$, $df=3$, $0.01 > P > 0.001$), and telophase I laggards ($G=12.14$, $df=3$, $0.01 > P > 0.001$).

In both species it is evident that, when scoring laggards at anaphase I, the **frequency of collapse is higher for early univalents**, that is, those having a stronger sister chromatid cohesion, than for equivalent numbers of late univalents. When laggards are scored at telophase I, the probability of collapse is increased with respect to anaphase I (compare the two stages in Fig. 6 A and B). In addition, the differences between categories of univalents diminish. This suggests that **those univalents persisting as laggards until telophase I are the ones directly related to spindle collapse**, and the difference between early and late univalents is mostly due to the more frequent occurrence of sister chromatid separation in the interval between anaphase and telophase in late univalents.

An additional control for the occurrence and frequency of spindle collapse was performed using fixed preparations from heat-treated males. In this case, a correlation was established in *E. plorans* between the mean number of univalents per cell at prometaphase I and the frequency of unreduced metaphase II cells (Fig. 7). The correlation found is high ($r=0.85$, $P<0.001$), and fits the data obtained in living cells. According to the correlation obtained in fixed preparations, cells with six univalents correspond to a frequency of 70% of diploid metaphase II (see Fig. 7), hence to a hypothetical collapse probability of 82% (70 diploid metaphase II plus 30 normal metaphase II, that is, 85 anaphase I cells in which 70 underwent collapse); this is very similar to the probability of 79% estimated in cultures. Thus, it can be concluded that the process of spindle collapse occurs within the testes of the heat-treated males very much as it occurs in cultured meiocytes.

Meiotic progression is normal in collapsed cells

After a collapse event, cells enter a diploid but, otherwise normal, second division (Fig. 3); the nuclear envelope breaks down, and a bigger but apparently functional second division spindle is formed to which the diploid set of chromosomes is capable of attaching, with separation of chromatids at anaphase II. This is followed by a normal telophase and cytokinesis II, producing diploid spermatids, which are common in heat-treated males. A direct correlation between spindle collapse and diploid sperm is difficult to establish, since the two events are so separated in time, but a rough estimation in a random sample of fixed preparations from heat-treated males yielded frequencies between 28% and 50% of diploid spermatids, which is one order of magnitude higher than any estimation in untreated males.

As shown in Fig. 3, the progression of collapsed cells is simultaneous with that of the normal cells of the same cyst. Moreover, in order to quantify any possible effect of the occurrence of spindle collapse on meiotic progression, a timetable was elaborated, to estimate and compare the duration of successive meiotic intervals as defined by the cellular milestones described previously. Cultures were classified into four categories:

1. Controls, without heat treatment and devoid of autosomal univalents.
2. Heat-treated cells, with or without univalents that did not collapse.
3. Heat-treated cells, all them with univalents, that underwent complete spindle collapse. Corresponding second divisions were diploid.
4. Heat-treated cells with univalents that underwent incomplete spindle collapse, showing an atypical, at least partial cytokinesis I. Only one of these cells was tracked until second division, which was diploid.

The average duration of each interval in these four categories is shown in Fig. 8. There are no conspicuous differences in overall duration between them, considering that the biggest difference is about 1 h compared with a total duration of between 15, noticeably, in collapsing cells, and 16 h. It can be concluded that **neither heat treatment nor the occurrence of spindle collapse alters the normal pace of meiotic progression.**

In an attempt to check more carefully for possible causes of spindle collapse, the influences of different factors on prometaphase I duration in *E. plorans* were specifically analysed by ANOVA with planned comparisons. Four factors were considered: heat treatment yes/no, presence/absence of univalents as a whole, number of univalents, and presence/absence of collapse for the four categories described above (see Fig. 9). The only significant effect found was a delay in anaphase I onset, averaging 45 min, due to the presence of univalents, but irrespective of their number ($F=5.61$; $P<0.05$) (Rebollo and Arana 1998). The possibility that spindle collapse is a consequence of such a delay is ruled out since the **duration of prometaphase I is the same in collapsing and non-collapsing cells with equivalent numbers of univalents** ($F=0.04$; $P>0.05$; see Fig. 9).

Discussion

One of the systems in which meiotic restitution has been most thoroughly studied is in interspecific or intergeneric hybrids of Gramineae. These hybrids show extensive asynapsis,

producing high (more than 20) numbers of univalents that, as prometaphase I proceeds, accumulate at the equatorial plate and lag at anaphase I (probably due to amphitelic stabilisation) (Wagenaar 1968a, b; Maan and Sasakuma 1977). Lagging chromosomes may show a certain degree of chromatid separation but anaphase I does not occur; instead, the chromosomes “become more diffuse and reform into a mass of chromatin around which a single nuclear membrane develops” (Islam and Shepherd 1980). Occasional bivalents that segregate correctly at anaphase I, together with “scattered”, non-aligned, univalents (probably syntelic), fail to be included in the main nucleus and form micronuclei that may remain in the same cell or may be separated by a cell plate. The formation of micronuclei at the polar regions indicates that spindle collapse has not occurred. Chromosomes seem to play a merely passive role in the process of restitution in these hybrids of Gramineae. Various authors agree that it is simply the accumulation of univalents at the equator that causes, in the first instance, a prolongation of prometaphase I. If the delay is too great (Wagenaar 1968a, b; Islam and Shepherd 1980), the cells return to an interphase state by breaking down the spindle and forming a nuclear envelope around chromosomal masses wherever they might be located in the cell. A higher degree of equatorial accumulation of univalents induces a longer anaphase I delay, hence an increased frequency of restitution. Hybrids producing higher numbers of viable, although polyploid, seeds are those where univalency is most extensive.

Our results do not quite fit this model; first, accumulation of univalents at the equator of the cell is not required for collapse to occur since cells with low numbers of laggards may collapse with a high probability (see Fig. 6). Similarly, we cannot conclude that collapse occurs in cells with a prolonged anaphase I delay. The moderate delay we find, due to the presence of univalents, is not related to spindle collapse, as the duration of prometaphase I is the same in collapsing and non-collapsing cells. In addition, the differences in the probability of collapse found between early and late univalents cannot be explained by a model that only takes into account the number of laggards and no other characteristics of the chromosomes. Finally, as has been described, the mechanism of restitution in hybrids of Gramineae implies a rearrangement of the cytoskeleton into an interphase state, which is obviously not true in our case, since **tubulin immunostaining demonstrates that during collapse, the spindle is deformed, but there is no evidence of disassembly.**

In animals, descriptions of the process of meiotic restitution are more scarce: Nicklas (1967) has reported an event similar to our spindle collapses occurring after amphiorientation of a micromanipulated bivalent in a living spermatocyte of the grasshopper *Melanoplus differentialis*. However, the most extensive study of restitution in animal meiocytes is that of Giménez-Abián et al. (1997), carried out in fixed preparations of desynaptic mutants of the grasshopper *Chorthippus jucundus*. These authors described cells with extensive univalent formation, showing at telophase I a circular arrangement of the diploid set of chromosomes around what appeared to be a single pole. They were postulated to have originated by a progressive approaching of the poles provoked by the pulling exerted by the kinetochores of amphioriented univalents. In these mutants, early anaphase laggards had linear stretched kinetochores. In circular telophase I cells, their kinetochores were horn shaped, pointing towards the centre. This was interpreted as the result of progressive bending of the kinetochores following the change in direction of the spindle fibres. Therefore, in these authors' model, chromosomal fibres are folded at the equator instead of persisting as straight

bundles that shorten as collapse proceeds. This indicates that, if kinetochore pulling is the initial trigger of spindle collapse, it is not the main cause of the continuous approaching of the poles.

Our results best fit a model in which **chromosomes play an active role during the whole process of spindle collapse** as follows:

1. Univalents, initially syntelic at prometaphase I, end up acquiring amphitelic orientation at metaphase I (Wagenaar and Bray 1973; Rebollo and Arana 1995, 1998; Giménez-Abián et al. 1997; Rebollo et al. 1998).
2. Anaphase A does occur in these cells but amphitelic univalents lag at the equator owing to the persistence of sister chromatid cohesion at the centromeric level, which is the rule at the first meiotic division (Miyazaki and Orr-Weaver 1994; Bickel and Orr-Weaver 1996).
3. **Kinetochore fibres of laggards do not disappear but stay in anaphase mode**, that is, sustaining microtubule depolymerisation, thus becoming shorter as collapse progresses. Depolymerisation at both the kinetochore ends and the polar ends of the fibre, or only at the latter, would yield the same result. In early anaphase, depolymerisation at both ends may contribute to the shortening of the fibres, whereas in late anaphase depolymerisation at the poles seems to prevail (Mitchison and Salmon 1992; Waters et al. 1996).
4. At this stage, whereas in normal cells spindle elongation takes place, in collapsing cells a conflict is established between the forces that tend to pull the poles apart, such as microtubule sliding at the zone of interdigitation, pulling of asters from the cell cortex and spindle pushing forces exerted on chromosomal arms (for review see Sharp et al. 2000), and the opposing traction force generated by kinetochore fibre depolymerisation together with maintenance of glued sister chromatids.
5. Besides the progressive shortening of kinetochore fibres, the **morphology of collapse in those cells with laggards positioned on one side of the spindle is also suggestive of this mechanism**. As shown in Fig. 4D, in asymmetrical collapses the spindle side containing laggards shows the typical folding of the mitochondrial mantle over the equator, whereas the side devoid of laggards shows a pronounced curve. This would be the expected appearance if poles were approaching by a **traction force exerted only on the side of the spindle where the chromosome is placed**.

The final result of the conflict depends on which of these opposing forces prevails. The traction force exerted by the kinetochore fibres on the poles increases with the number of laggards. This causes the **positive correlation found between the number of univalents, or laggards, and the frequency of spindle collapse**. If any of the chromosomes lagging at the onset of anaphase I succeed in segregation, they no longer contribute to the traction force exerted on the poles. This accounts for the difference between early and late univalents: sister chromatid cohesion is weaker in late than in early univalents, so, in the former, a higher proportion of laggards achieve equational segregation before telophase I, then fewer chromosomes continue to exert a traction force on the poles and the probability of collapse diminishes. When only those laggards that do persist until telophase are considered, there are no marked differences between early and late univalents.

During the development of collapse, the architecture of the cytoskeleton does not progressively turn into an interphase state; rather, the traction force is capable of destroying the rigid microtubule lattice supported by the interdigitation of microtubules, folding it over the equatorial plane to form the lateral projections that confer on the collapsing cells their particular flattened shape. The sideways displacement of furrowing to the lateral projections in collapsing cells facilitates nuclear restitution and hence meiotic progression. Regarding this, two facts are noticeable: first, furrowing may occur despite the abnormal parallel alignment of microtubules in the lateral bundles. Second, the midbody-like structures in collapsed cells lie at the same distance from the poles as the midbody does in normal cells, suggesting that the **signals for furrowing, initially at the equator of the cell, move together with microtubules during collapse**. This supports the role of the central spindle in the determination of cytokinesis (Wheatley and Wang 1996; Glotzer 1997 for review).

The causal relationship between univalency or, more properly, anaphase lagging and collapse does not concern only the first meiotic division, because, after equational segregation, single chromatids may trigger the same process in the second anaphase. Single chromatids lagging at anaphase II may appear in both normal, and unreduced second division cells since it is possible that, even in those cells collapsing at anaphase I, some univalents complete equational segregation. Restitution at the second division has been found in plants forming univalents (García-Velázquez 1991) and, in some cases, restitution has been reported to occur in both meiotic divisions, producing a wide range of ploidy levels (Ferris et al. 1992).

The biological significance of nuclear restitution varies depending on the system; as mentioned before, it may be related to parthenogenesis or it may have played a role in the evolution of allopolyploid groups as a mechanism that partially restores fertility after hybridisation. However, in our material these putative roles seem unlikely: it affects male meiosis so cannot be related to parthenogenesis and there is absolutely no evidence that allopolyploidy has played any relevant role in the evolution of Orthoptera (White 1973; Cuéllar 1987).

The induction of spindle collapse by the activity of lagging chromosomes implies a confrontation between the forces that normally act in the cells at these stages of meiosis. Considering that polyploidy reduces gametic, zygotic or embryonic viability more strongly than aneuploidy alone – data from human fetal chromosomal abnormalities seem to confirm this point, as polyploidy is much more rare in liveborns than is aneuploidy (Niebuhr 1974; Carr and Gedeon 1977; Hassold 1986) – the final yielding of the spindle microtubular framework to the pulling exerted at the chromosomal fibres results in a **reduction in biological wastage**, as the resulting polyploid cells do not proceed so far as aneuploid cells into embryonic development. At least at the frequencies estimated in our material, meiotic restitution could account for the discarding of a considerable proportion of abnormal cells at a relatively low biological cost. In this sense, restitution may be considered a lucky mechanism contributing to alleviate the effects of univalency in those cells where nonexchange chromosomes tend to amphiorient (in *E. plorans* the frequency of amphitelic orientation of univalents is 65%, but in *L. migratoria* it reaches 90%). Amphioriented chromosomes would not be detectable by the metaphase-anaphase transition checkpoint, as they are attached to the spindle, aligned, and under tension. As we have seen, however, amphioriented laggards represent an enormous source of abnormalities (Rebollo and Arana 1995, 1998). Thus, we find it reasonable to think

that if there were genetic variation in the facility of spindle collapse, those alternatives determining a higher frequency of restitution would be selectively advantageous.

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Table 1. Modes of segregation after anaphase I lagging in autosomal univalents of *E. plorans* and *L. migratoria*.

(No. us, number of univalents)

Species	Category	No. us		Orientation		Segregation of laggards					
		No.	us	%		Syntelic	Amphitelic	Equational	Reductional	Collapse	Migration failure
						No. us	%	No. us	%	No. us	%
<i>E. plorans</i>	Early	134		50		37		84	63		5
	Intermediate	298		117		39		181	61		1
	Late	82		23		28		59	72		20
	Spontaneous	46		17		37		29	63		3
	Total	560		207		37		353	63		29
<i>L. migratoria</i>	Early	80		7		9		73	91		25
	Late	122		15		12		107	88		91
	Total	202		22		11		180	89		116

Fig. 1. Curves of response to heat treatment in different males of *Eyprepocnemis plorans*. Frequency of univalents per cell is estimated at prometaphase I. **Thick segments** are the actual estimations of univalent frequency; each individual was sampled twice, on consecutive days to place it unequivocally in the ascending or descending part of the response curve. **Thin segments** are tentative representations of the evolution of univalency with time in each individual. Two individuals with early univalents (uninterrupted lines), two with intermediate (dashed lines), and one with late (dotted line) univalents are represented. Note the variation between individuals in the temporal response to heat, as one of the two individuals analysed on day 16 shows a mean number of univalents per cell above 10 (intermediate univalents) and the other shows a mean lower than 1.5 (late univalents).

Fig. 2. Cellular milestones used for the elaboration of the meiotic timetable in *E. plorans* cultures. PM I nuclear envelope break-down marking the beginning of prometaphase I. **A I** anaphase I onset. **COLL** spindle collapse, completed when the two chromosomal masses associated with the poles are in contact. **CYT I** complete cytokinesis I. **NE I** complete reassembly of the nuclear envelope after the first meiotic division, either around the two daughter nuclei or the single restitution nucleus. **PM II** nuclear envelope breakdown at the beginning of prometaphase II. **A II** anaphase II onset. **CYT II** complete cytokinesis II. **NE II** nuclear envelope formation after the second meiotic division.

Fig. 3A–H. Legend see page 295. **A** Anaphase I. The spindle of the collapsing cell flattens while the others elongate. **B** Telophase I. Most normal cells have initiated cytokinesis. The collapsing cell shows the mitochondrial mantle as two lateral projections at the equatorial plane; in normal cells mitochondria form two lines perpendicular to the equator. **C** Collapse is complete. The nuclear membrane is formed around the restitution nucleus. Cytokinesis is complete in normal cells. **D** Interkinesis. Note the larger size of the collapsed cell during the whole of the second division. **E** Nuclear envelope breakdown at the beginning of prometaphase II. **F** Metaphase II. Chromosomes are perfectly aligned in all cells. **G** Anaphase II. No segregation abnormalities are seen in the collapsed cell. Anaphase onset occurs in synchrony with normal cells. **H** Telophase II and cytokinesis also occur normally. Bar represents 10 μ m.

Fig. 4A–G. Legend see page 298. **A** Complete anaphase I spindle collapse in *E. plorans*. Normally dividing chromosomes have already reached the poles (0 min print) whereas two amphioriented laggards stay at the equator (**double arrowheads**). There is a progressive approaching of the poles (12 min print) until the decondensing chromosomal masses fuse (33 min print), and the nuclear membrane is formed around the unreduced nucleus (240 min print). **B** Complete anaphase I spindle collapse in *Locusta migratoria*. Two laggards appear in focus in the 0 min print. Note the progressive folding of the mitochondrial mantle (0 and 8 min prints) until the formation of two lateral bands (20 min print, see also 33 min print in Fig. 3A). The smaller size of the *L. migratoria* spindles is evident compared with those of *E. plorans*. **C** Incomplete anaphase I collapse in *E. plorans*. Each of the two approaching chromosomal masses (61 min print) forms its own nuclear envelope (143 and 315 min prints). Cytokinesis is absent, resulting in one single daughter cell with two closely associated nuclei (315 min print). **D** Asymmetrical anaphase I collapse in *L. migratoria*. One laggard located on the right side of the spindle (0 min print) provokes a collapse in which only this side shows the typical folding of the mitochondrial mantle, whereas the other side shows a pronounced curve (9 and 14 min prints). The lateral band forms only on the right-hand side of the spindle (24 min print). **E** Complete anaphase II spindle collapse in *E. plorans*. A single chromatid originating from equational division at anaphase I, lags at anaphase II (0 min print) and provokes the progressive approach of the poles of the second division spindle (0 to 25 min prints). Cytokinesis is absent and a restitution nucleus is formed (164 min print). The folding of the mitochondrial mantle is also evident. **F** Incomplete anaphase II collapse in *E. plorans*. One lagging single chromatid, showing a persisting chromosomal fibre (0 min print), prevents normal spindle elongation and cytokinesis (23 min print), producing two connected daughter cells (63 min print). Bar represents 10 μ m. **G** Spurious lateral furrowing (arrowheads) on both sides of a telophase I collapsed meiocyte in *E. plorans*. Bar represents 10 μ m.

Fig. 5A–J. Tubulin immunostaining of normal and collapsing meiocytes of *E. plorans*. **A** Normal prometaphase I meiocyte. **B** Normal anaphase I. **C** Normal early telophase. Cytokinesis has started, and a dark band is appearing at the central spindle (arrow). **D** Normal late telophase. Nuclear envelope formation is complete. Cleavage has progressed and the midbody is clearly visible (arrow). **E, E'** Initial stage of a collapsing anaphase of *E. plorans*. The spindle is flattening instead of elongating (compare with the same stage in a normal cell in **B**). One amphioriented laggard is in focus, showing an intact chromosomal fibre, binding each sister kinetochore to its respective pole. Polar microtubules first bend and then progressively fold over the equatorial plane, leaving the centre of the spindle relatively empty. **F, F'** A more advanced anaphase I collapse. The chromosomal fibres of several laggards are visible in **F**; they shorten as collapse progresses. Some of the laggards are separating chromatids while others persist undivided (**F'**). As a result of the flattening of the spindle, lateral bundles of microtubules are starting to form. This implies the disorganisation of the antiparallel bundling at the zone of interdigitation without depolymerisation. The intertwining microtubules presumably pivot on one another to end up forming parallel bundles that correspond to the lateral projections detected under phase contrast by the disposition of the mitochondrial mantle (see Figs. 3 and 4). **G, G'** A later stage of collapse. The chromosomes from both poles have established contact. Segments of straight persistent chromosomal fibres associated with laggards are in focus. The microtubule lateral projections have grown as the poles approach. **H** At a later stage, the two chromosomal masses are fused and chromosomes start decondensing. Chromosomal fibres are no longer visible. Each of the two lateral projections shows a dark band in the middle, resembling the one formed at the central spindle during normal telophase/cytokinesis, and approximately at the same distance from the poles (compare with **C**). **I** Restitution nucleus at late telophase I. The nuclear envelope is formed around a nucleus bigger than normal (compare with each of the daughter nuclei in **D**). Microtubules are rearranging in the interphase mode, but lateral bundles persist and still show the dark bands resembling the midbody present

in normal cells at this stage (compare with **D**). Bar represents 10 μ m. **J** Second division collapses show single chromatids attached to both poles by chromosomal fibres.

Fig. 6A, B. Frequency of spindle collapse versus number of laggards at anaphase I and telophase I in living meiocytes of *E. plorans* (A) and *L. migratoria* (B).

Fig. 7. Frequency of diploid metaphase II cells plotted versus the mean number of univalents per cell at prometaphase I in fixed preparations of heat-treated *E. plorans* males.

Fig. 8. Average duration (hours) of meiosis I and II intervals in *E. plorans* cells classified according to treatment and presence/absence of spindle collapse. Controls consist of untreated cells, lacking autosomal univalents; **non-collapsing** cells include treated cells, either with or without autosomal univalents, that did not undergo spindle collapse; **collapsing** cells are those heat-treated cells, possessing univalents, that underwent complete spindle collapse, therefore lacking cytokinesis; and the group named **collapse and cytokinesis** includes those treated cells, with univalents, that underwent incomplete spindle collapse and at least partial cytokinesis. Abbreviations: **Pm I** prometaphase I, **A I** anaphase I, **Cyto I** cytokinesis I, **Coll** spindle collapse, **NE I** nuclear envelope formation after the first division, **Pm II** prometaphase II, **A II** anaphase II, **Cyto II** cytokinesis II, **NE II** nuclear envelope formation after the second division.

Fig. 9. Prometaphase I duration in *E. plorans* versus the factors considered for statistical analysis: heat treatment, presence and number of univalents, and presence/absence and mode of spindle collapse. Only the presence of univalents, irrespective of their number, produced a significant effect on prometaphase I duration: a moderate lengthening.